

The Valuation of *Nettiquette* of Primary Teachers in Digital Era

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Abstract: Internet etiquette is very necessary as teachers increasingly use the internet in teaching and communicate online. Netiquette is introduced in schools so that teachers would be more ethical in utilizing and dealing with the dynamics of interactions in the digital space wisely. The purposes of this study were to know the level of teachers' understanding on netiquette in digital use and to describe factors that influence it. This study used phenomenological research method. The data were collected through observation sheets which distributed to 15 teachers from several schools on google form. The results indicated that the majority of teachers already understand that in cyberspace, humans interact and communicate with various cultural differences. Easy internet access allows everyone to connect and participate, without cultural or geographic boundaries. So, netiquette needs to be implemented by all internet users, both in the field of education and social media. Cyber-bullying is a case that needs to be recognized and anticipated as early as possible. For this reason, apart from teachers, it is also important to socialize netiquette to all students at elementary to high school levels.

Keywords: Netiquette, primary teachers, digital competence.

INTRODUCTION

Currently the industrial revolution has reached the fourth stage or better known as industrial revolution 4.0, where development not only leads to increasingly digitalization of tools, but also to the push to improve human quality so that they are able to keep up with change. One of the big steps to balance the changes in the industrial revolution 4.0 is the need for digital competence as a provision that every individual needs to have. Especially in the field of education, teachers as an integral and crucial part of learning need to have digital competence. Teacher digital competence in education 4.0 is the ability to integrate both physical and non-physical technological components in the learning system to answer human

resource needs to create digital opportunities full of creativity and innovation in the world of education (Qureshi et al., 2021).

Based on survey results from the Indonesian Internet Service Providers Association (APJII), internet users in Indonesia reached 215.63 million people in the 2022-2023 period. This number increased 2.67% compared to the previous period, namely 210.03 million users. The number of internet users is equivalent to 78.19% of Indonesia's total population of 275.77 million people (Admin, 2023).

Digital literacy has become an important skill in the current information and technology era. For both teachers and students, digital literacy has a significant impact in advancing the learning process and optimizing the learning experience. Here are some important benefits of digital literacy for teachers proposed by Nopitasari et al (2023) ; (1). Increasing creativity in learning. Teachers with strong digital literacy can develop creative and innovative learning approaches. Teachers can design interesting learning materials by utilizing digital tools, such as videos, images and interactive multimedia. (2). Access a wider range of learning media resources. Digital literacy allows teachers to easily search, select and use various credible online learning resources. This can be in the form of learning videos, digital books, journals, and other educational materials that support the teaching process. (3). Learning differentiation capabilities. With digital literacy, teachers can be more effective in adapting learning to meet students' individual needs. They can utilize online learning platforms to provide different assignments according to students' ability levels and interests. (4). Collaboration and sharing with fellow teachers. Digital literacy provides teachers with the opportunity to engage in online learning communities, where they can share experiences, teaching strategies, and resources with fellow teachers from different parts of the world.

Digital Ethics is an individual's ability to realize, exemplify, adapt, rationalize, consider and develop digital ethical governance (netiquette) in everyday life . Kusumastuti et al (2021) state 4 indicators of digital ethics , namely; (1). Internet ethics. Internet ethics consists of 3 indicators. They are; know the importance of implementing ethics on the internet, know the various communication standards that exist on each social media platform, and understand what to upload and what not to upload when using social media and other digital devices. (2). Beware of negative content. The negative content warning consists of 2 indicators, namely; know the type of information that contains hoaxes, hate speech, pornography, bullying and other negative content and understand the impact of being a creator or disseminator of information that contains hoaxes, hate speech, pornography, bullying and other negative content. (3). Meaningful interaction in digital spaces. Meaningful

interaction in digital space consists of 2 indicators, they are; know how to interact, participate and collaborate in digital spaces according to applicable ethical rules and regulations and understand the various regulations that apply when interacting, participating and collaborating in digital spaces. (4). Interact and transact wisely. Interacting and transacting wisely consists of 2 indicators, namely; know the types of electronic interactions and transactions in the digital space in accordance with applicable regulations and understand how to interact and conduct electronic transactions safely in the digital space. So, all digital activities – in digital spaces and using digital media – require digital ethics or netiquette.

Several definitions have been carried out to define similarity netiquette standards. “netiquette” is a combination of “internet” and “etiquette” understood as the perception of online culture as a derivative of offline culture (Heitmayer & Schimmelpfennig, 2023). So, it can be interpreted that online etiquette is part of offline etiquette, and thus internet users must be wiser when surfing the internet and communicating via the internet. Digital social norms are dynamic and change over time. They depend on the capabilities, institutions and competencies contained in the digital installations and users they regulate, such as the platforms on which interactions take place. Moreover, it could be argued that to understand the conventions of digitally mediated interactions, we need to free netiquette from etiquette and think of it as independent entity. Establishing netiquette as a digital social norm will help make this happen. In other words, online interactions are influenced by a wide network of external and environmental factors, one of which is offline culture.

In addition, to help cyber novices minimize their mistakes, and to help experienced cyber explorers help novices there are 10 golden rules of netiquette proposed by Shea (1996). The rules are: (1). Remember humans. You must behave as you would like others to behave towards you. You have to understand if you are in someone else's position. because via the internet you can't see facial expressions, body movements, or hear the voice of the person you're talking to, so you have to be really wise when writing online. (2). Adhere to the same standards of online behavior as in real life. Actually, we can usually act according to existing regulations in real life. But online, people sometimes don't remember that there is a human being they are interacting with. (3). Know where you are in cyberspace. Every place has different netiquette. What is accepted in one place, may not necessarily apply in another place. So, if we want to participate in a domain, we have to understand for a moment the chat style and appropriate topics. (4). Respect another people's time and bandwidth. Today's people tend not to have much time to spend long periods of time reading or listening to conversations in cyberspace. so we must be able to create effective and efficient messages.

(5). Make yourself look good online. Apart from that, make sure what you write is clear and logical. don't try to impress someone by using a lot of long words that you don't really understand. It's better to keep it simple. (6). Share expert knowledge. If you have knowledge that can be shared, it's a good idea to share it online. because from one question you ask, various answers can emerge that indirectly enrich your knowledge related to the topic you are sharing. (7). Helps control flame wars. "Flaming" in the cyber world means a person's expression that is expressed without holding back the slightest emotion. This tradition of free expression has been around for a long time, indeed sometimes it can be entertainment for some people. However, it would be good if we faced a situation like this, we could wisely control it so that it does not become a source of dispute or problem that could trigger conflict. (8). Respect another people's privacy. Everyone has privacy that they don't want other people to know. When we use the internet, we should also understand these limitations. one of them is being presumptuous in reading other people's emails. This is strictly prohibited because apart from ruining friendships, we can also lose colleagues and even jobs. (9). Don't abuse your power. If only you have greater intelligence and power than other people, don't just take away other people's rights or use them to seek profit in cyberspace. everything has rules. (10). Forgive other people's mistakes. Always trying to be kind when you see other people's mistakes or shortcomings in cyberspace is very wise. There are times when people make spelling mistakes, ask unimportant questions, or answer questions ineffectively and in long but meaningless writing. So, if we want to respond to this, think twice, try to be polite in private emails rather than criticizing in public.

Along with the development of online education and online courses, Internet users in the world of education will speak through writing both to fellow students and teachers, so it is very important to communicate well and professionally. Columbus University (2013) mentions five important notes regarding netiquette in the field of education, including:

1. Be friendly, positive and reflective. we must be very careful in expressing ourselves. every word and writing must be thought carefully before sending it. Don't respond to something in a state of anger and use language that is easy to understand.
2. Use appropriate language and titles. Avoid using slang or even dirty words. calling others by appropriate names. Using caps lock is also not recommended because it seems sarcastic and shouts anger.
3. Use effective communication. Before sending a comment or message, read it again and make sure it doesn't offend the person who receives it. We also need to be careful when joking, because if it is said at the wrong time, other people will respond negatively.

4. Professionalism. The use of smiles or other emoticons must also be appropriate to the person you are talking to, especially when talking to a teacher or tutor. Not all teachers like the use of emoticons in online messages. Also avoid using informal abbreviations. In every message, it is best to say please and thank you.

5. Ask for clarification. When you are unsure about what you said or heard, don't hesitate to politely ask for clarification. Don't just stay silent when you don't understand something. If you want to interrupt, wait for the right moment until there is a pause for open interaction, so you can explain it precisely and clearly.

The development of digital communication has the characteristics of global communication that is cross-border geographical boundaries and cultural boundaries. Meanwhile, every geographical and cultural boundary also has different ethical boundaries. Every country, even region, has ethics itself, and each generation has its own ethics. For example, regarding privacy.

Likewise, with digital interactions between genders and between other social groups. All will raise ethical issues. This means that in the digital space we will interact, and communicate with various cultural differences, so it is very likely that this global meeting will give birth to new standards on this matter ethics. Netiquette must take a step beyond literacy and skills-based notions. It is not enough to simply use netiquette as a label for "how-to" style guides and "tutorials" that provide training for specific skills, for example, behaving properly on forums or in email conversations. Instead, we define netiquette as a complex network of interrelated digital social norms that govern the way humans interact with each other in digital contexts. Therefore, the author is interested in analyzing the netiquette that teachers have in one elementary school in the city of Padang. Through this study, it is hoped that the author will be able to describe the level of netiquette that these teachers have and what factors influence it.

METHOD

Study Design

A phenomenological research was used in this research. This approach is intended to examine human experiences in everyday life while setting aside researchers' preconceptions about the phenomenon. In other words, phenomenological research investigates real experiences to learn more about how individuals perceive those experiences (Bliss, 2016). In its implementation, this research was conducted in the form of a survey which revealed the netiquette knowledge of teachers who teach in elementary schools in the city of Padang. The concept of the method used is in accordance with the concept that aimed at uncovering ideas

that exist in society relating to certain problems. The results of this research will be presented in the form of a descriptive presentation relating to the object studied.

Participants

The subjects in this research were teachers who taught at some state elementary schools in Padang. All subjects in the research are population. Therefore, the population in this study is all teachers in schools related to internet ethics. Due to the large number of individuals in the population involved, sampling is necessary.

The sampling method used is probability sampling, namely simple random sampling of observation individuals selected in such a way that each has an equal and independent opportunity to be selected and targeted as a potential sample respondent (Noor et al., 2022). Meanwhile, the research objects in this study were 15 teachers from several schools regarding questions about the netiquette of digital as stated in the research questionnaire.

Technique of Collecting Data

To obtain data related to the research problem, several data collection methods were used, as described below:

1. questionnaire

The questionnaire used in this research is closed questions (Hyman & Sierra, 2016). This questionnaire is distributed via Google form. It is stated that the advantages of web technology are useful in designing, developing and obtaining user responses in a simpler way (Vasantha & Harinarayana, 2016). For the first group, the questionnaire will be structured into several parts. In the first part, participants will be asked to provide information regarding gender, age, address, subjects taught, and preferred device used to access the Internet. In the second part, participants will be asked questions about teachers' understanding on netiquette. Answers to all sections will be filtered through a nominal scale which is a measurement mechanism where the answer to a particular question can fall into any category.

The following are the indicators and sub-indicators of the digital ethics module (Kominfo, Siberkreasi & Deloitte in kusumawati et al (2021):

1. Internet ethics (netiquette)

- a. Know the importance of implementing internet ethics
- b. Know the various community standards that exist on each social media platform
- c. Understand what should and should not be uploaded when using social media and other digital devices

2. Knowledge of information that contains hoaxes, hate speech, pornography, bullying, and other negative content.

- a. Know the type of information that contains hoaxes, hate speech, pornography, bullying and other negative content
- b. Understand the impact of being a creator and disseminator of information containing hoaxes, hate speech, pornography, bullying and other negative content

3. Basic knowledge of interaction, participation and collaboration in digital spaces in accordance with digital ethical rules and applicable regulations.

- a. Know how to interact, participate and collaborate in digital spaces in accordance with digital ethical rules and applicable regulations
- b. Understand the various regulations that apply when interacting, participating and collaborating in digital spaces

4. Basic knowledge of interacting and transacting electronically in the digital space in accordance with applicable regulations.

- a. Know the types of electronic interactions and transactions in the digital space in accordance with applicable regulations
- b. Understand how to interact and transact electronically in the digital space

Because this study is only limited to netiquette, the author narrows the scope of the questionnaire to only the realm of netiquette. Based on literature and theories, the author compiled 10 questions in a questionnaire for 15 teachers as respondents.

2. Interview

An interview is a discussion with open answers. Interviews conducted with 5 selected respondents who live in Kuranji Village, Padang City.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results

The Level of Teacher Understanding of Netiquette

The level of teacher understanding of the concept of netiquette in integrating digital technology and learning materials can be seen from their general knowledge about netiquette related to pedagogy. Teachers need pedagogical knowledge in the use of digital devices in planning and implementing learning. The results can be seen in the following chart:

Chart 1. The level of Netiquette of Primary teachers

The graph above shows that around 37% of teachers know that netiquette is an etiquette rule on the internet. Only 17% understand it as a net for catching fish. Meanwhile, 27% consider it a crime against other people on Facebook and the remaining 20% actually understand it as good manners at the dinner table. In the second question, 40% were aware of one form of cyber-bullying, namely posting provocative images. 23% of teachers thought this was a discussion about political views. Meanwhile, another 13% chose C, namely sharing someone's post. The remaining 23% see it as someone's posting of information online.

Then, when asked what was meant by shouting on the internet, 47% of teachers answered that using all caps was the answer. Only 17% would consider screaming at the computer. 10% of teachers choose to put lots of exclamation marks at the end of sentences. Another 27% feel they don't respond to friend requests on Facebook. When asked about who can see information typed in chat rooms in the fourth question, 15% thought it was only the people they chatted with. 19% of teachers prefer anyone who is on the web at any time. Then, another 23% only consider the people you are with at the computer. The remaining 43% thought it could be seen by everyone in the chat room at that time.

In addition, in the fifth question, as many as 25% of teachers immediately opened and responded to emails received from unknown people. Only 9% felt the need to contact the police. 24% of teachers decided to delete without opening the email. Meanwhile, another

43% leave emails in their inbox until they find out where they come from. On the eighth question about information that should not be shared on the internet, 12% thought that they should not mention their name, another 28% chose not to mention their age. Meanwhile, 48% of teachers think that the address is the most confidential thing and another 12% think that it is not permissible to share anything, including name, age or address on the internet. Furthermore, in the seventh question regarding how to avoid cyber-bullying, 23% of teachers chose to reveal personal information to anyone who asked. 16% decided to attack first. As many as 46% feel the need to obey netiquette rules. Another 15% ignore all online friend requests.

In the eighth question about what they would do if they experienced cyber-bullying, 42% of teachers decided to tell someone they trusted or someone older. Another 27% felt there was no need to tell anyone because it would be embarrassing. 20% of teachers think they should delete everything about them on the internet. Only 11% felt this should be reported to the police. Understanding of cyberspace is asked in the ninth question. 6% think that if no one can see our presence, then no one can judge. 28% of teachers think you will be graded based on what you do on the internet. 49% think that you will be judged based on your intentions on the internet, if you never hurt anyone, then everything will be fine. Meanwhile, another 17% think that you will be judged based on your profile photo. The final question asks what behavior you should not do if you get an embarrassing picture from someone. 17% thought they should tell their parents or teachers. Another 19% decided to tell someone else. Meanwhile, 10% of teachers replied to the person who sent the image. Another 55% refused to send it to anyone else.

Based on the results of the questionnaire, it was found that 12 out of 15 teachers knew about the concept of netiquette in digital technology, namely everything related to digital ethics in sharing personal information, avoiding cyber-bullying, shouting over internet, responding to email, and judging in cyberspace.

Just like a community, a digital forum also has certain rules and regulations, where these rules relate to limitations and the best way to use internet facilities (Rahim & Yustiana, 2023). The development of the digital revolution 4.0 provides challenges and opportunities in various fields, including education. As the spearhead of education management, teachers are required to be able to adapt and utilize technological developments. Teacher competency must also be adapted to learning needs in the digital era.

The data was further analyzed using inferential statistics. Next, Multiple ANCOVA was used to analyze the influence of mastery of netiquette on teachers' digital competence. The results can be seen in the following table:

Tests of between-Subject Effects

Dependent Variable: Netiquette

Source	Type III Sum Of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	9024,675 ^a	5	1728,827	14,964	,000
Intercept	63112,038	1	76112,039	545,751	,000
Digital competence	2110,722	1	1120,733	8,055	,005
Netiquette	1604,108	2	1253,605	101,126	,000
Digital Competence*Netiquette	1724,307	2	816,657	6,749	,003
Error	4430,713	33	132,453		
Total	146388,000	39			
Corrected Total	13674,500	37			

R Squared = ,667 (Adjusted R Squared = ,618)

The results of the ANCOVA test show that the F count for the independent variable of the digital competence netiquette is F count = 101.126 with a significance value of 0.000 ($0.000 < 0.05$). Therefore, knowledge about netiquette influences teachers' digital competence. As we know, the challenges in implementing netiquette are very big, because etiquette is more closely related to our individual personalities, so not all internet users obey these rules. But actually, netiquette is not a complex thing, as long as our logic and common sense run smoothly, we will have no difficulty implementing it because netiquette comes from common and ordinary things that we do in social life (Kusumastuti et al., 2021). This netiquette is also closely related to mastering digital literacy soft skills which is part of the self-development that we must have.

Factors that Influence Understanding Netiquette in Digital Competence

The role of educators is needed to guide students to have good communication ethics, as well as the control that parents give their children in using devices. Aspects of the friendship environment outside of school can also influence the negative impact and delinquency resulting from the use of social media. Children's misbehaviour that comes from outside the school environment can be brought into the school, it is feared that it could have a negative impact on friendships in the school environment, so it is hoped that students will have communication ethics that can be applied to friendships in person and in cyberspace.

In the digital world, we also know internet ethics or what is better known as Netiquette, namely ethics in using the internet. The most basic thing about netiquette is that we must always be aware that we are interacting with real humans on another network, not just with a row of characters on a monitor screen, but with real human characters.

The importance of digital literacy skills for students to help them prepare themselves to face globalization. In the elementary school environment in Kuranji sub-district, there are no specific activities to provide digital literacy education for students. Teaching and learning activities have been carried out in a technical form or use of technology, but have not yet shown how the technology is used safely, intelligently, kindly and wisely. Schools can innovate in forming students' digital ethics as young citizens in a good digital era, in order to meet their knowledge, attitudes and skills through various forms of digital literacy education, with good netiquette knowledge, which can be a provision for interaction between friends. takes place in real life.

The results of the interview shown that most of the teachers pointed out that ethics can simply be interpreted as good rules that every individual must obey in life social. In relation to communication, they further emphasized that ethics is a self-associative process, namely an endless search process using various moral rules both explicitly and implicitly. Ethics is related to respect, care, and is related to good communication individual and social, in other words ethics regulates our ways communicate with each other as moral human beings.

Discussion

The finding of this study has figured out several facts. When we communicate and transact in the digital world, we are required to be able to select and analyse what information we will convey to the person we are talking to in the digital world. Because what we are dealing with are both humans who have hearts and feelings. So, we have to carefully select the rules for using appropriate language, for example communicating with people who are older, of the same age, or younger, either via email or social media. We should adjust the language used to suit each context. We can use this competency to choose and sort out behaviour that is in accordance with netiquette and behaviour that is not in accordance with netiquette.

Therefore, even though interactions in the digital world where we can all express ourselves more freely without limits because of the borderless effect of the internet, that doesn't mean we can do whatever we want. As with ethics in social life, the sanctions that can be obtained for a violation of ethics or applicable norms are social sanctions and legal

sanctions. Social sanctions can take the form of a reprimand or even exclusion from social life. Likewise, if there is a violation of netiquette, the sanctions that will be received could be exclusion from the life of the digital community.

All transaction information that occurs on social media cannot be separated from ethical aspects. Netiquette or internet ethics are the rules and procedures for using the internet as a means of communication or data exchange between a group of people in an internet-mediated system (Tedre et al., 2006). In addition, Fahrimal (2018) highlights several guidelines that we need to pay attention to when accessing the internet and social media, namely; (1) Be constructive, show positive attitudes and comments constructive to others so that they will gain constructive feedback as well; (2) Be safe, make sure every post you post doesn't upset anyone others feel uncomfortable both physically and emotionally; (3) Remember, we're all human even if there is no contact directly with other people, remember that your network is a human who has feelings; (4) Avoid flame, don't create tension with other people, If there is a debate, then discuss the thoughts and ideas not attack the person; (5) Choose your words carefully, before commenting or make posts on the internet and social media then choose the right words or sentences; (6) Avoid "death by emoticon" use the right emoticon Express your expressions and don't overdo it use it; (7) Accept the views of others, interactions on social media are the process of exchanging ideas and concepts, then respect every opinion provided by different parties; (8) Freedom of speech may not exist, there is no freedom have absolute opinions on the internet, then limit yourself in choosing which ones will be displayed or posted and which ones needs to be ignored.

This real opportunity encourages primary teachers massively to develop their motivation and competence in empowering technology and digital devices in the learning environment. In theory, there are nine elements that are the focus of learning in elementary schools today, including differentiation of place and time of learning, individual education, student independence in determining learning styles, project-based learning, direct field experience, interpretation of information and data, evaluation in various ways and aspects, student involvement in determining teaching materials and resources, as well as assistance in building independence (Syahid et al., 2022). The presence of these nine trends creates a new direction in education and learning practices in Indonesia which liberates students in learning and teachers in teaching. The success of curriculum and learning in education 4.0 depends on teacher competence in understanding, managing, developing and evaluating the use of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) and digitalization in the education sector.

The school digitalization program will be supported and followed up by increasing teacher competency, especially in the field of mastery of ICT. This is because teachers are the spearhead and determinant of the success of the school digitalization program to accelerate the creation of superior Indonesian human resources.

In this modern era, advances in information and communication technology have brought significant changes in various aspects of life, including the world of education. The use of digital platforms has changed the way students and teachers obtain, process and share information. Digital literacy has become a crucial skill that must be mastered by all individuals, especially students and teachers, in order to face the challenges and opportunities in facing an increasingly connected and complex world (Bahri et al., 2022).

The main challenge of modern society today is the use of the internet and media digital which not only provides benefits to its users, but also opens them up opportunities for various problems to occur. Lack of netiquette knowledge in using hardware and software give rise to uses of digital media that are not optimal. A weak digital culture can lead to violations of digital rights resident. Low internet ethics has the opportunity to create a digital space that does not exist fun because there is a lot of negative content. The fragility of digital security is potential for personal data leakage or digital fraud. The integrity referred to in this case is honesty. Digital media that is potentially manipulative, easy, and provides enormous content tempts its users to act dishonestly. Copyright violations, for example, plagiarism, manipulation, etc. are examples of integrity issues. Responsibility relates to the impact or consequences resulting from an action. So, responsibility means the willingness to bear the consequences of one's behavior. While virtue concerns things of beneficial value, humanity, and kindness

CONCLUSION

In short, netiquette should be adhered to by every individual in particular millennial teachers in interactions on the internet and social media. The expression offered by the internet is limited freedom. The most obvious limitation is the social system and living arrangements in the neighbourhood where you live. System social communication on social media is exactly the same as communication systems in everyday environments, so that manners as well as other ethical values need to be upheld tall. Non-ethical behaviour on the internet and social media is very difficult controlled because each person can have more than one account with fakeable pictures, but at least understanding netiquette is a guide for the millennial teachers to be more internet literate.

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